

Researchers' experiences of publishing academic books open access: Posters

These posters were produced by Insights Media for UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) as part of a project to develop case studies on the experiences of researchers who published their books open access. The case studies are the outcome of interviews with the researchers who participated in the project. The interviews were conducted in 2024. The views in these case studies are those of the researchers and do not necessarily reflect the views, priorities, and policies of UKRI.

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“Being an early adopter of publishing openly has been very beneficial to my career”

Janneke Adema, Associate Professor in Digital Media at The Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University

Adema says there shouldn't be any barriers to accessing research. Nor does she believe in waiting to put a finished product out there.

When it's suitable and appropriate, she believes in open practice throughout the research lifecycle, from the initial conception of a research idea and the planning stages, data collection and sourcing information, through to analysis and publication.

An early blogger, she has regularly invited others to collaborate with her and engage with her work as it progresses.

She explained: “Communicating my research is something I've always done, right from the start of my academic career. I've always put as much as possible on my blog and shared it – my work in progress, my research presentations, my conference presentations and my papers.”

How publishing open access benefits Adema

Highly visible and transparent approach creates a buzz

Collaborative approach engages other researchers

Raises profile early in your career

Bigger and broader reach for your work

Breaks down barriers to your work

**“So much is available
electronically now
– it’s transformational.”**

Gwyn Bevan, Emeritus Professor
of Policy Analysis in the
Department of Management
at the London School of Economics
and Political Science

“How Did Britain Come to This?”, is Bevan’s latest book. Published open access, it had over 3,000 downloads in the first nine months.

Based on his experience, Bevan thinks technology and open access publishing have changed academia for the better. People can access and publish research more easily and freely, and research is more easily found and read. This leads to higher reader numbers, a more diverse readership and more citations. Academics gain a much higher profile, as does their research.

Bevan thinks that in the future, people who chose to publish through more traditional routes will be at a disadvantage. “Stuff you can access electronically will get read and cited, and stuff which you have to buy as a book or go to a library or access behind a paywall, will not do as well, will not have the same reach or citations.”

**How open access
and digital have been
transformational for Bevan**

Knowledge is easily and freely available. It’s at your fingertips, not shut away in a library, including important documents and primary research

The research process is faster and enriched by the depth and breadth of material that is available

People, academics and the general public, have much greater access to his research, amplifying its reach

“Open access allows for multimedia work in a different way. I couldn't imagine publishing this work in a more traditional format.”

Francesca Coppa, Professor
of English, Theatre and Film
Studies at Muhlenberg College

Open access publishing is rooted in the digital age. As a result, Coppa says it encourages innovation, such as new ways of creating and producing research. It enables academics to play around with form and content and to make the most of digital publishing. This suits Coppa, who is a strong advocate of remix cultures and transmedia storytelling. Her research explores how stories overlap across text, video, theatre and image, so it was essential when she published her latest book that the output included and reflected the actual research.

Coppa said: “It's a book about video artists, so it was really important to me to include clips and examples of the art.”

How open access publishing benefitted Coppa's research

It supported experimentation around form, content and style

It is multimedia, enabling Coppa to include videos, clips, images and links connected to the research

The research output was designed to suit the research material and message

“Knowledge doesn’t benefit anyone if it’s inaccessible.”

Martin Paul Eve, Professor
of Literature, Technology
and Publishing at Birkbeck,
University of London

Research has impact when people can access it, engage with it and build on it.

Eve firmly believes that open access book publishing enables that greater impact, facilitating the dissemination of knowledge by removing geographical and financial barriers. He says this creates a more equitable world, one where scholars and people everywhere can easily find and use knowledge. Eve has mobility issues so open access publishing enables him to access knowledge easily, while at the same time amplifying his voice through enabling him to reach a wider audience.

He says: “It’s had a very positive impact on my career. And I have much greater satisfaction and purpose in what I do, knowing there’s a much broader audience for my work. People who don’t engage with open access are missing out on a huge opportunity to do good in the world.”

Eve says open access book publishing drives impact

It breaks down access
barriers

Access drives engagement
and that creates impact

It disseminates research
to a bigger, wider audience

Knowledge is used and
built on more widely

Improved access
encourages diversity
of thinking and debate

“Knowledge should be freely available.”

Jean-Paul Faguet, Professor
of the Political Economy of
Development at London School of
Economics and Political Science

Academics working for wealthy institutions in the Global North don't always realise the access issues facing academics working for less wealthy institutions, particularly those in the Global South.

Faguet says open access publishing helps address issues of inequality, which he feels is particularly important in his area of research. He wouldn't like to be conducting fieldwork and gathering data and then putting it all behind a paywall where only those at elite institutions in the Global North can access it.

“The people we study live in developing countries, and the results, conclusions and recommendations – the main point of this research – is really aimed at developing countries, first and foremost.”

Why Faguet believes in open access publishing

Research reaches people who need it

Knowledge is shared equitably around the world

Data and evidence can be used for the greater good

It stops research from being extractive

“Change has to come from more established scholars.”

Aileen Fyfe, Professor
of Modern History at the
University of St Andrews

Open access book publishing is on the rise but Fyfe says many academics still shy away from it. She fears many senior academics also advise early career scholars to take the well-trodden, prestige publishing route, thinking it is safer and will open more doors.

Fyfe thinks this is a shame and that senior academics need to agitate for change. She published her first open access book in 2022 in collaboration with three post-doctoral researchers and says it has been a hugely positive experience.

It wasn't a decision she took lightly. She too was concerned that it would affect the career prospects of her early career researchers, but the reality has been very different. The book has generated a lot of interest, with 1,800 downloads in the first month. One of Fyfe's researchers has since published their own book open access, and is working on another.

Fyfe says senior scholars need to get behind open access book publishing.

“We need to see senior members of the profession speaking out in favour, demonstrating that it can be done and that the publishing process is very similar in terms of editorial boards, peer review and copy editing.”

Fyfe's advice on how senior scholars can break down barriers

Share how open access increased their profile and visibility: Fyfe saw 1,800 downloads in one month

Show it can (and should) be done with rigorous and quality publishing standards

Share the benefits of born-digital publications, like flexibility of format and style

Challenge perceptions in their communities and organisations

“Whose knowledge counts? Whose knowledge is available? Whose knowledge circulates widely?”

Dr Ellie Gore, Lecturer in Global Political Economy in the Department of Politics, University of Manchester

Who does and who doesn't have access to knowledge is something Gore cares deeply about. They think research should be easily and freely available. When publishing their book, *“Between HIV Prevention and LGBTI Rights: The Political Economy of Queer Activism in Ghana”*, they chose open access to ensure there weren't any geographical or financial barriers and that everyone who participated in the research could access it.

Academics, activists and institutions in the Global South often have limited access to research due to the cost of academic books and paywalls.

By publishing open access, Gore says anyone and everyone will have access, regardless of where they live.

Research that circulates widely also tends to have more impact. It is more likely to stimulate debate, challenge established narratives and influence policy, for example.

That is important to Gore: “I'm hoping it's not just academics and researchers that read it. I'd like to think it is of interest to policymakers, activists, civil society organisations in Africa and around the world who are concerned about LGBTI rights and the struggle for queer liberation.”

Publish your book open access
www.oabooks-toolkit.org

Why Gore believes equity of access is important

Knowledge should be available to everyone who wants and needs it

People shouldn't be disadvantaged because of their location or economic position

Research can be circulated far and wide

Different voices and perspectives can surface

Some of the ongoing Global North – Global South power imbalances can be addressed

“I’m a strong believer that open access is the way to go for works that have been publicly funded, but there is still a pejorative sense that open access means self-publishing.”

Roger Kain, Professor of Humanities at the School of Advanced Study, University of London

Kain feels that attitudes to open access publishing are slowly changing. This is partly due to the ability for academics to reach a bigger, more diverse audience, the influence that research has when it's disseminated more widely and the higher citations numbers. However, Kain says many scholars in management positions are still of the view that it is an inferior publishing choice and advise early career researchers against it.

But, Kain thinks the momentum for change is building and that the younger generation of academics will move the debate forward.

“The generation of researchers who were early career five or so years ago and are now coming through to the mid-career stage – they are going to carry a very different view of open access to people of my generation.”

Why Kain thinks attitudes to open access publishing are changing

Higher reader numbers

The ability to influence thinking is greater

Higher citation numbers

People believe in equitable access to knowledge

Attitudes to digital publishing are evolving

“It rapidly became clear that an incredible number of downloads were taking place, all over the world. The free on demand PDF was the big feature.”

Geoffrey Khan, Regius Professor of Hebrew at the University of Cambridge and general editor of the open access series Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures.

Khan made the switch to open access publishing because he wanted to reach a wider audience. He wanted his books to be read. His previous books had very low circulation figures, less than 100 sales, which is the norm with traditional scholarly publishing.

That changed almost overnight when he published his next book open access. It has been downloaded nearly 16,000 times so far. Citations have also increased.

Khan says it has been the same for the other authors publishing through his open access series. He says it is important that research is disseminated widely and freely, so that it goes beyond academia and the confines of traditional publishing.

“There is a genuine thirst for access to scholarship, a hunger for knowledge which goes beyond academic institutions.”

Why Khan believes in publishing open access

Research outputs reach a wider audience within academia

Research goes global

Research extends beyond academia

Research is more influential when people can access it, engage with it and use it

Digital, a cornerstone of open access publishing, drives accessibility

“Publishing my book open access makes it easier for me to disseminate knowledge, meaning my work is more widely known across the world.”

Professor Marie Lall, Chair
of Education and South
Asian Studies at the UCL
Institute of Education

By publishing her latest book – *“Myanmar’s Education Reforms. A pathway to social justice?”* – open access, Lall ensured that people in the Global South can read it, not just a handful of academics in the Global North. That means academics, policy makers, activists, the general public and the people who participated in the research, all have access to it. This was hugely important to Lall. She thinks academia should make it as easy as possible for people to access important research so that no-one is shut out and research can have maximum impact.

Lall said: “Myanmar has had a coup. Nobody can go to a bookshop, nor do they think to spend money on a book, but they will click on a link and read it.”

And they are clicking on the link, so far, the book has been downloaded 37,724 times in 173 countries, including 2793 of those downloads happening in Myanmar.

It would have been a very different story had Lall chosen to publish with a traditional press. Access would have been very limited, particularly in the Global South.

Why Lall supports publishing books open access

It ensures equitable access to research and knowledge

Dissemination is greater

It stops research from being extractive

Change is more likely if policy makers and activists can access research

“Being able to share research across boundaries is a great thing. It’s how knowledge can make a difference.”

David Luke, Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa at the London School of Economics and Political Science

Winner of the BCA African Business Book of the Year Award 2024, publishing open access has been good for Luke’s research and his profile.

The judges liked the open access approach, praising the book for breaking down barriers and being globally accessible. It was assessed on its merits, quality and global reach, not from a proxy measure.

When research is good, open access amplifies it, as has been the case for Luke. He has been invited to speak about his research, including a visit to the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in the US.

Greater access to thinking drives change. “Research should be shared among scholars, among people who can use the research,” says Luke.

How Luke thinks publishing open access benefits research and researchers

Research reaches a bigger audience, including the Global South

Drives impact as insights, ideas and information are shared and acted on

Open access enhances the integrity and rigour of research by increasing the opportunity for findings to be scrutinised

“A lot of the presses I like are scholar-led, embedded within their academic disciplines. You have this quality to it, because it’s being not just submitted by an expert, it’s being shaped by an expert in the field, edited by one and sometimes even copy edited by one.”

Dr Samuel Moore, a scholarly communications specialist at Cambridge University Library, is an early career researcher publishing his first monograph open access through a community press.

Open access facilitates community-led publishing, which Moore thinks is a very positive development. It encourages experimentation with form, content and audience participation, while adhering to the same high standards as traditional publishing.

Moore explains: “Publishing open access felt to me like a traditional publishing experience in terms of copy editing, peer reviews and such like.”

Moore’s advice for finding a credible open access book publisher

Tap into the rise of community, scholar-led presses

Pick a professional press with high publishing standards

Check the quality of the process, that peer review, copy editing and the editorial board all adhere to high standards

Look around because there are options

“To create more fully democratic access to knowledge across the world, we would also need to ensure that authors in other countries can not only read but also publish without having to pay.”

Joanna Page, Professor of Latin American Studies at the University of Cambridge, Director of CRASSH

Page says academia needs to radically rethink how knowledge is shared and paid for to ensure equitable dissemination around the globe.

Determined that her research should be freely accessible to anyone and everyone, she always publishes open access. She says it is both easier to achieve and less costly than people expect.

“I’ve never had to pay to publish an open access book and don’t believe I should. You aren’t limited to publishers that advertise open access routes.”

Page’s tips on open access publishing

Ask publishers if they publish open access (this is not always advertised)

Find out if a publisher has a waiver scheme

Some publishers run pilot initiatives

If a publisher requires a fee, check if there is a waiver scheme or another source of funds.

Funding is often available from a number of sources, e.g., institutional funds.

“My book is different from the traditional reading experience. I didn't want it to be the sort of book that symbolises knowledge and configures readers as receivers of knowledge.”

Matthew Reynolds, Professor
of English and Comparative
Criticism at Oxford University

According to Reynolds, “*Prismatic Jane Eyre: Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages*” was never going to be an ordinary book. Just as *Jane Eyre* is not just an English book – it has been translated into many different languages, with each translation creating shifts in interpretation, understanding, language, voice and style. There are now many Janes, says Reynolds, who led the *Prismatic Jane Eyre* research project, which culminated in an open access volume.

Reynolds collaborated with many academics from around the world and he wanted the book to reflect the international input and the nature of the work – that literature is not restricted to one language, one interpretation or one voice.

He said: “Reviewing all this work by translators and publishers in different locations is creative work. It's collaborative and creative, remaking and discovering new significances in new locations.”

Being open access and born digital, there was much more flexibility over the book's form, language and content. The different authors had more freedom to write in their own voice and style, and the text includes digital interactive maps and verbal animations.

Reynolds says this approach helps break down disciplinary and traditional academic silos, leading to greater creative expression.

Reynolds thinks publishing open access benefits research

It enables authors to explore the potential of digital

It breaks down barriers, encouraging interdisciplinary working

New ways of publishing encourage innovation and new research outputs

It encourages diversity of thinking

“I wanted to make a difference. I want to have an impact on the world and I want the world to be a better place.”

William Sutherland, Professor of Conservation Biology and Director of Research at the University of Cambridge

According to Sutherland, when he started his career in conservation, he realised that many libraries around the world weren't well stocked. As a result, many academics and community groups in the Global South in particular didn't have access to the latest research and thinking.

So instead of receiving royalties from his early books, the money was spent on sending out free copies to people who would benefit from his work.

Digitisation opened up new possibilities. Research could be made available to people around the globe at the click of a button, paving the way for open access publishing.

But, access is still restricted – many academics have to pay for books or to get past paywalls.

Sutherland said: “Books are only accessible to a limited number of people and where there's the greatest need for conservation, these books are hardest to acquire and hardest to afford.”

Sutherland thinks open access publishing helps academics make a difference

Research has greater reach

Readers can access the latest research, insights and evidence

Geographical barriers are removed

Financial barriers are removed

There is greater equity of access

“I think open access is terrific for people early on in their career.”

Jane Winters, Professor of Digital Humanities and Director of the Digital Humanities Research Hub at the University of London

Senior academics often advise early career researchers to publish with a traditional press. They say publishing a book open access could harm their career prospects. But, when Winters was the editor of an early career researcher book series, she found that open access book publishing was hugely beneficial to the fledgling scholars she worked with. Their work rapidly gained a high profile, getting their names noticed in academic circles. From that, they gained lots of networking opportunities.

“The early career researchers benefitted enormously from the attention their open access books got. And they were able to cross-promote each other’s work, building a real community around that. It was really effective in career development terms.”

More established scholars also benefit from open access book publishing – they too reach a wider audience, and more quickly, increasing the likelihood of their research having an impact. And the research process and quality of output is richer and potentially stronger because academics can easily access a more diverse range of source material.

Why Winters thinks publishing a book open access is good for early career researchers

It boosts research dissemination

It is good for profile building and networking

It can create a buzz around research

There are presses specifically aimed at new scholars